

CATCH-UP PRACTICES SELF-ASSESSMENT

Goals, Objectives, and Strategies

GOAL	OBJECTIVE	TARGET STRATEGY	ASSESSMENT	PRIORITY
Quality of Care	Implement COVID Testing Guidelines	Protocol for COVID Testing		
		Testing Quality Control		
		Report results to Health Department		
		PPE Protocol (Fit Test)		
		Patient and practice education		
	Implement Adult Immunization Guidelines	COVID		
		Influenza		
		Pneumococcal		
		Zoster		
		Tdap		
	Implement COVID Management Guidelines	Quarantine Recommendations		
		Outpatient Treatment Protocol		
Follow-up and Monitoring Progress				
Post-COVID Syndrome				
Financial Security	Better Primary Care	Infection (COVID) Registries		
		Cost of New Procedures		
		ED/Hospital transition protocol		
	Document, Code & Bill	EHR/PMS changes		
	Data-driven Quality	QI team, dashboards, measures		
		Improve information technology		
Joy in Practice	Teamwork	Huddles, roles, protocols		
		Staff turnover & burnout		
	Patient Centered Care	Patient survey or PFAC		
Healthy Community	Infection Control	Community COVID spread reduction		
		School/workplace infection control		
	Vaccination	Community vaccination campaign		

ASSESSMENT

CODE

Not answered	0
No protocol and/or not used	1
Partial protocol, rarely used	2
Partial protocol, used some of the time	3
Protocol, used most of the time	4
Protocol, used all the time	5

PRIORITY

Assign a priority to each Target Strategy from 1 to 5 with 1 being most urgent. You may have multiple items with the same priority.

